

Quantifying the Impact of Flood Attack on Transport Layer Protocol

KULDEEP TOMAR¹ AND S.S TYAGI²

¹Research Scholar, Department of CSE, MRIU, Faridabad, Haryana, India

²Professor & Head, Department of CSE, MRIU, Faridabad, Haryana, India

ABSTRACT

As growth of internet and computer increase day by day so as the growth of attacks on network is also tremendously increased day by day. In this paper we introduced a wired network and create two TCP source node and one attacker node (Distributed denial-of-service) flooding type attack which is the attack on the bandwidth of TCP node at source side sends data to destination through router and also measure the impact of Denial-of-service attack (DoS) on that wired network how packets of other source nodes and that node will drop down due to the impact of flooding type denial-of-service attack and shows the result using NS-2 NAM & Xgraph windows in simulation.

Keywords

CBR, DoS, DDoS, NAM, TCP, Wired Network .

1.INTRODUCTION

In Today's world, network security is major concern in computer network. There are so many attackers who spoof the important information and misused that information through these kinds of attacks on network attackers spoof the information. Denial-of-service is not only the issue in the internet but rather it changes the mandatory or required information when there would be slight change in the protocols. The emergence of Distributed denial-of-service exists in the base of the Internet architecture [1] and there are so many methods through which we will detect the DDoS attack as in [2][3]. There are following types of attacks that come against the infrastructure of Internet.

- Attack against TCP/IP
- Attack against DNS
- Attack against Border gateway protocol

And there are some attacks that comes under the wired network

- Denial of Service Attack
- Modify the information
- Escalation
- Destruct the data
- Disclosure

In this paper we introduce the DDoS attack (Distributed denial-of-service) called Flooding type Attack which is on the bandwidth of the network. Denial of service attack divided in following three categories:

- Flooding type Attack
- Protocol Attack
- Logical Attack

We consider the attack on bandwidth introduced on the wired network and measure or calculate the impact of flooding DDoS attack on the TCP protocol. We experimentally show the result of flooding attack by network simulator NS-2. In which change the bandwidth range and the result is shown as packets will drop down at the node 3 called router node r1.

In Transport layer TCP and UDP are the two protocols on which impact measured. We consider the TCP protocol and measure the performance of TCP protocol by Xgraph and NAM output files. As we know the TCP is connection oriented protocol and every time before packet sends to destination the connection would established.

2.BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

There are following comparative study and experiments implemented on TCP and UDP protocols, detecting denial-of-service flooding type attack on TCP & UDP. In this we analyse the quantitative description of flood type on the bandwidth & its results on packets drop other source nodes at router. In [4] we analyse the study on transport layer as now we study application layer protocol with the traffic CBR, Expo, ftp etc. as we recognize DDoS is single most important threats for the recent Internet as of its ability to generate a enormous volume of redundant or not needed(unwanted) traffic[5].however the number of techniques have been anticipated to conquer denial-of-service attacks in Distributed Peer-to-peer networks, it is still extremely inflexible to react to the flood based DDoS attacks due to a huge number of attacking technology and make use of this type of technology to spoof the source- address. A well-organized structure has been considered to detect and defend from the Distributed denial-of-service attacks in Peer-to-Peer networks. It prevent against these type of threats or attacks by allowing to maintain the distance among source and the dupe end [6].In the following category of threat, an attacker attempt to avoid the use or release of a valuable resource to their intentional viewers or clients. It may be implemented by the use of various methods, in reality and on computer device. For example, any attacker can disallow everyone to access telephone systems by cutting down the main telecom wire from a building, by repetitively calling each accessible phone line, or by distort their PBX [7]. Up to now we understand the work of malicious node[8] on wired network and on transport layer now we study the effect of malicious node that attacker node on wireless network also as in [9][10][11] attacker node affect the zone or on wireless network area. There is also a protocol which works as defender in DDoS [12].

3.EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

In this paper our work is on the TCP protocol and we implement the result with 4 type of traffic (CBR, FTP, Preto and Exponential) as architecture shown in fig. 1 below:

Figure.1 Architecture of Wired Network with Attacker node

In this architecture 2 nodes called as a user node (TCP node) S1, S3 in network and S2 is attacker node (TCP Node) which will affect the both source node s1, s3 called 0, 2 and s2 is attacker node 1 and r1 is router node called 3 and d1 is destination node called 4 in the fig.2 and results shows the performance of each traffic on the TCP by the bandwidth. Data sends from node0 is 0.2 MB so only 20% data is send from node0 to r1 and 55% data sends from node1 attacker node to r1 so that traffic will affect the node0, node2 so the packets from node0,node2 will be drop down due to attacker node traffic. Node2 sends 45% traffic to r1, and r1 sends 20% data to d1, as shown in results.

In TCP/IP the TCP is transport layer protocol in which attaches the traffics to TCP node and algorithm is shown as:

1. Create a Simulator
set st[new Simulator]
2. Select the colors
\$st color 0 red
\$st color 1 green
\$st color 2 blue
3. Set the shape
\$ no Shape"circle"
\$ no Color"black"
Same for n1, n2, n3, n4
4. Set the three output files as f_name as f0,f1,f2
5. Create the five nodes as
set n0 [\$st node]
set n1 [\$s tnode]
set n2 [\$st node]
set n3 [\$st node]
set n4 [\$st node]
6. Create the duplex/simplex link between the nodes as source node n0 to router n3 and attach the delay and bandwidth in the queue(RED/DropTail) as set the data %

```
$st duplex-link $n0 $n3 0.2 Mb 100ms
DropTail
```

```
# set the Attacker node as means 55% data send from attacker node
```

```
$st duplex-link $n1 $n3 0.55Mb 200ms
DropTail
```

```
$st duplex-link $n2 $n3 0.45Mb 300ms
DropTail
```

```
$st duplex-link $n3 $n4 0.8Mb 100ms
DropTail
```

#For creating TCP Agent steps are

7. set tcp1 [new Agent/TCP]
8. \$st attach-agent \$node \$tcp1
9. \$tcp1 set class_ 2
10. set sink1[newAgent/TCPSink]
11. \$st attach-agent \$n4 \$sink

12. #Connect the traffic (CBR/ Expo/ Preto/ftp) source with the traffic sink

13. \$st connect \$tcp \$sink1
14. \$tcp1 set fid_ 1

15. #Following steps are the parameters of CBR

```
#Setup a CBR over TCP connection for node n0, n1, n2
Set cbr1as [new Application/Traffic/CBR]
$cbr1 attach-agent $tcp1
```

15.1 #Parameters of CBR

```
$cbr1 firstly set type of traffic as set type then
$cbr1 set packet_size
$cbr1 set rate
$cbr1 set random
```

#And for exponential traffic parameters steps are:

```
#Setup a Exponential over TCP connection for node n0
set exp0 [ new Application / Traffic/ Exponential ]
```

15.2 #parameters of expo traffic are

```
$exp0 attach-agent
$exp0 set packet_size
$exp0 set burst_time
$exp0 set idle_time
$exp0 set rate
```

#And for FTP traffic parameters steps are:

```
#Setup a FTP over TCP connection for node n0  
set ftp [new Application/FTP]
```

15.3 #parameters of ftp are

```
$ftp attach-agent $tcp1  
$ftp set type_ FTP
```

16. Then record the procedure for bandwidth.

Figure.2 Architecture of 5 nodes

Fig. 2 represents the 5 nodes wired scenario in which packets send from s0 i.e. 0 to r1 (router) i.e. 3 and through the router to d1 i.e. 4 at that time packets send by only S0 and no data sends from S1 i.e. the attacker node so no data will drop at r1. As and in fig. 3 represents the packets will drop down due to S1 sends packet to r1 so the packets of S0 and S3 are drop down.

Figure.3 Packets Drop of node0 and node2 due to node1

Even also the Effect of this attacker node, S1 will also drop the packets at some time in the Network as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure.4 Packets of node1 also drop down at r1

Now the results analysis is shown by the graph at which time packets will drop down and how the peak called bandwidth will be changed as packets rate fig.5 shows the experimental graph result of exponential traffic in which the packets of node0 will drop down at 1.43 as shown in fig.3 and in graph of fig. 5 also as we known exponential distribution is on/off traffic distribution at one time only traffic sends to destination.

Figure.5 Result analysis at Exponential node

In the fig. 6 the experiment shows the result of ftp traffic on the network as every traffic has different parameters as discussed in above algorithmic steps. Due to their parameters each will drop down packet on different time period as in fig.6 packets will drop down Between 1.00 to 1.5 as shown by the bandwidth.

Figure.6 Result Analysis at FTP Traffic

As the same in Fig.7 results of bandwidth is shown for Preto type traffic.

Figure.7 Result analysis of preto traffic

Another type of traffic is CBR (constant Bit rate) traffic in which traffic sends at constant bit rate through the help of its following parameters. The packets drop at 2.0 as shown by bandwidth in graph of fig.7.

Table1. Traffic Parameters

Parameters	Value
Traffic type	Distributed Denial-of-service(DDoS)
Traffic generation at attacker	TCP

Traffic arrival at TCP	CBR, FTP. expo, Preto
Packet_size	1000
Rate	100k
Ideal_time	1ms
Now time	0.1

In this experiment the simulator used for these above results is NS-2 that is a platform on which source and attacker node sends the packet and due to attacker node packets drop down and throughput comes in the form of Xgraph shows in above results of traffic shows how packets sends and how many packets sends to d1 and how packets flow and drop down in a network. In above results different types of traffic is generated at TCP nodes 0,1,2 and each traffic would have following parameters to generate that traffics and due to their parameters each will drop out there packets at different time period in the graphs.

4.CONCLUSION

The experimental analysis shows the flooding of packets by S1 will affect on the bandwidth of network so the less packets will reach to destination and packet drop rate shows here in results because of the different traffic generators at attacker node and other nodes.TCP is Connection established protocol so less packets will drop at r1 as comparison to the UDP node and more no. of packets will send at d1.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank all the researchers and the authors of referred papers for their contribution in this area.

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Authors

Dr. S. S. Tyagi is presently working as a Professor and Head of the Department of Computer Science and Engineering in Manav Rachna International University, Faridabad, Haryana, India. He is having an experience of 22 years including 4 years of industrial and 18 years of teaching experience. He has been holding various academic and administrative positions during his career. He has been consultant to some software development companies. He has been an examiner and evaluator for M.Tech thesis and PhD thesis. He has been a reviewer for books and research papers for some renowned and reputed journals. He is guiding 07 Ph.D. Scholars in the field of Network Security, Ad hoc networks, Cloud Computing, Wireless Security etc. There are around 40 publications to his credit published in reputed International Journals, National Journals and in the proceedings of International and National Conferences and contributing to the research for the benefit of mankind and society at large. His knowledge covers all major areas of Computer Science and Engineering. Currently his areas of research interest are Network Security, Wireless Communication, Mobile Ad hoc Networks, and Cloud Computing. Dr. S. S. Tyagi, is a member of various professional bodies like IEEE, CSI, QCI, ASQ etc.

Kuldeep Tomar is a Research Scholar in the Department of CSE, MRIU, Faridabad, Haryana, India. He has done M.E/M.Tech in Computer Science and Engineering from C.I.T.M., Faridabad, India. He has a total work experience of 12 years (including academics and industry) in different organizations. He is currently working as Associate Professor in NGF College of Engineering & Technology, Palwal, Haryana, India. He has published more than 17 papers in reputed International Journals, National Journals and in the proceedings of International and National Conferences etc. Has is also written a book. He also is a member of Computer Society of India, Membership No: N1039627.